

Development of co-sputtered amorphous Ge-Bi-Se films for nonlinear infrared photonic applications

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ABSTRACT: RF magnetron co-sputtered amorphous Ge-Bi-Se films were fabricated using polycrystalline GeSe₂ and Bi₂Se₃ targets. Their structural, linear, and non-linear optical properties were studied to understand compositional influence for future photonic applications. A broader Ge-Bi-Se amorphous region with a noticeably high Bismuth atomic percentage (up to at. % Bi = 36%) is observed using this deposition method compared to ≤ 16 at.% in the conventional Ge₂₀Se_{80-x}Bi_x bulk glass synthesis¹. The structural characteristics of the co-sputtered films were analyzed using Raman spectroscopy where increasing bismuth concentration shifted all vibrational bands to the lower energy side with reduced intensity. A decrease in optical bandgap energy values from 2.04 (± 0.2) eV (Bi at. % = 0) to 0.73 (± 0.2) eV (Bi at. % = 36) and the corresponding increase in refractive index value n from 2.4 (± 0.01) to 4.09 (± 0.01) at telecommunication wavelength indicate the strong influence of bismuth on optical properties of films. Third-order nonlinear optical parameters were calculated from linear parameters using semi-empirical equations and Sheik-Bahae formalism in order to allow their prediction according to the film composition and taking into account the wavelength of use. Following these simulations, which enabled the selection of promising compositions in terms of optical non-linearity applications, this work also focused on demonstrating the feasibility of manufacturing ridge waveguides from these co-sputtered films by RF magnetron using dry etching with the aim of offering Ge-Bi-Se-based integrated optical circuits.

1. INTRODUCTION

Amorphous chalcogenides have attracted much scientific attention and have been extensively investigated due to their properties and potential applications in various fields such as infrared sensors, phase change memory devices, waveguides, solar cells, optical switches, acousto-optical instruments, microstructured chalcogenide glass optical fibres etc. ²⁻⁶. The peculiar properties like wide Infrared (IR) transparency, low phonon energy, significant optical non-linearity, memory switching behaviour and photo-induced effects ⁷⁻⁹ were the primary reasons that make chalcogenide glass a sought-after material in improving future technologies. Another crucial advantage of the chalcogenide glasses is their wide compositional tunability, expanded glass forming region, with singularities including compositional and configurational disorders or formation of new defect centres ¹⁰.

The incorporation of bismuth in the Ge-Se glassy system results in remarkable changes in the Ge-Bi-Se system's physical, optical, chemical, electronic and structural features ¹¹⁻¹². A number of studies have been carried out on Ge-Bi-Se thin films fabricated by different Physical Vapor Deposition methods and based on the study of one or other of these properties, some of which can be cited here. Optical and structural properties of vacuum-evaporated Ge-Bi-Se thin films were investigated in refs ¹³⁻¹⁴, and in particular, it was found that the optical bandgap energy decreases with increasing Bi concentration. Mawale et al. performed stoichiometric analysis of the clusters generated during the interaction of laser pulses with Ge-Bi-Se thin films using laser ablation time-of-flight mass spectrometry ¹⁵. M.M. Hafiz et al. investigated the photoinduced effects in Ge-Bi-Se glassy thin films and found that photobleaching is dominant in $\text{Ge}_{20}\text{Se}_{80-x}\text{Bi}_x$ ($x=0, 2.5, \text{ and } 5$ at.%) while photodarkening becomes dominant in Bi richer $\text{Ge}_{20}\text{Se}_{72.5}\text{Bi}_{7.5}$ thin

films¹⁶. T Rajagopalan et al. have also analysed the crystallisation behaviour of thermally evaporated Ge-Bi-Se thin films¹⁷.

Generally, amorphous chalcogenides show p-type conductivity, and the transition from p-type to n-type conductivity with the addition of Bi into Ge-Ch (Ch = S, Se, Te) chalcogenide glass system is an active research area. Bismuth's large polarizability and metallic character result in a p-n-type carrier reversal¹⁸⁻²⁰. Mathew et al. reported a significant decrease in photoconductivity and carrier lifetime in $\text{Ge}_{20}\text{Bi}_x\text{Se}_{80-x}$ composition with $x \geq 7$ ²¹. The role of bismuth in electrical conduction transformation is still ambiguous. According to Elliot and Steel²², the formation of new ionic Bi-Chalcogen bonds and structural defects results in unpinning the Fermi level and subsequent carrier reversal. Kounavis et al. performed a detailed study of the defect distribution in $\text{Ge}_{25}\text{Bi}_x\text{Se}_{75-x}$ sputtered films and found that the addition of Bi causes an increase in density of states (DOS) at the valence band (VB) side, resulting in shifting of Fermi level and change in majority carrier sign from positive to negative²³. Photoemission and inverse photoemission studies in amorphous $\text{Ge}_{20}\text{Se}_{80-x}\text{Bi}_x$ thin films also underline the p-n transition by adding Bi²⁴. Lone pair electrons in the valence band, the presence of localised states as well as defects states in the mobility gap have a crucial role in the light-induced property modifications of chalcogenide materials²⁵⁻²⁶.

If we now consider more specifically the optical properties associated with their potential nonlinearity, we can briefly recall that selenium-based chalcogenides are promising candidates for nonlinear optical (NLO) applications^{5,27}. Very few studies on third-order nonlinearity and related applications have discussed the influence of bismuth presence on the non-linear optical properties of Bi-Chalcogenide films. Researchers predicted nonlinear refractive index n_2 and nonlinear susceptibility χ^3 values of bismuth-incorporated chalcogenide films (BiSeTe,

GeInBiSe, AsBiSe) using generalised Miller's rule and Tichy & Ticha semi-empirical relations²⁸⁻³⁰. All of them reported an increase in ONL values with increasing bismuth concentration, which drew our attention to the potential offered by germanium-based films in which antimony has been substituted by bismuth, the toxicity of which is less widely reported.

Let's look in more detail at the methods used to manufacture chalcogenide thin films. The RF magnetron co-sputtering is an efficient method for preparing amorphous chalcogenide thin films with wider glass-forming regions beyond their bulk counterparts³¹. Different compositions can easily be achieved by varying the power applied to individual cathodes with sputtering targets³². Thus, the existence of a larger amorphous zone than what can be obtained with bulk glasses could be explored with significant concentrations of Bi in the co-sputtered Ge-Bi-Se films without studying their optical properties¹⁵. Other previously reported studies have used sputtering with a single target or thermal evaporation from glass targets of defined composition^{16-17, 23, 33-35}. It, therefore, seemed important to explore the Ge-Bi-Se thin film system to confirm the extent of the amorphous region and to fully appreciate its optical and structural properties for potential photonic applications.

The purpose of the present investigation is to perform an extensive experimental study of the fabrication of amorphous thin films from the Ge-Bi-Se system via radio-frequency (RF) magnetron co-sputtering through GeSe₂-Bi₂Se₃ tie-line and to analyse the effect of bismuth on the optical characteristics as well as other physical parameters, especially in the near-infrared to mid-infrared wavelength range. A detailed theoretical calculation of nonlinear optical characteristics (n_2 , non-linear absorption coefficient β , figure of merit (FOM = $n_2/\lambda\beta$)) from linear parameters in between 1.55 to 4 μm wavelength is also carried out for the first time in Ge-Bi-Se composition. The lack of experimental results necessitates theoretical calculation of non-

linear optical parameters for understanding the Ge-Bi-Se system with a view to their use in future non-linear photonics. This study also explores the possibility of etching these thin films to design single-mode integrated photonic waveguides from RF magnetron co-sputtered Ge-Bi-Se films on Si/SiO₂ substrate. The correlation between etching parameters and Ge-Bi-Se waveguide sidewall roughness is also reported for the first time.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Physical vapour deposition system MPE600 (Plassys-Bestek, Marolles-en-Hurepoix, France) was used for the preparation of co-sputtered Ge-Bi-Se thin films using the RF mode at room temperature. Following processing parameters and conditions were held constant throughout all depositions, (a) argon flow 75 sccm, (b) argon working pressure 0.5 Pa (0.5 Pa for co-sputtering, 0.5 Pa and 1 Pa for single source depositions), (c) target-to-substrate distance 9 cm, (d) substrate holder rotation 5 rpm, (e) background pressure $\leq 1 \times 10^{-5}$ Pa. Commercially available polycrystalline GeSe₂ and Bi₂Se₃ sputtering targets were used in cathode 1 (C1) and cathode 2 (C2) respectively. Different substrates, BK7 glass, single crystal silicon wafer (<100>), and Si/SiO₂ (~2000 nm SiO₂ layer on Si <100>) were selected for different characterisation purposes. To equally cover the whole compositional range of the pseudo-binary GeSe₂-Bi₂Se₃ system, power ranges of between 5 W and 37 W for C1 and between 5 W and 20 W for C2 were applied. C2 power was kept lower due to the higher deposition rate of Bi₂Se₃. Thin film compositions were determined by C1 and C2 power ratios, while thicknesses were determined by deposition durations, as reported in ref³².

X-ray diffraction studies were conducted on films deposited on BK7 substrates to confirm their amorphous nature using Rigaku Mini-Flex 600 with 2 Theta in the 10° – 90° range with step

0.02°. Chemical compositions of prepared films were analysed by energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) using LYRA3 TESCAN equipped with an EDS analyser (Oxford instrument) at an accelerating voltage of 10 kV. For analysing constituent elements, L-lines were selected for Ge and Se, and the M-line was set for Bi. The average value of quantitative measurements at five different spots was taken to get the final composition.

Optical transmission spectra of films were taken at 180–3300 nm wavelength range using UV-VIS-NIR Spectrophotometer UV-3600 Plus (Shimadzu, Japan). The optical functions of prepared films were determined by variable angle spectroscopic ellipsometry (VASE, J. A. Woollam Co., Inc., Lincoln, NE, USA). UV-VIS-NIR VASE was used in the 300-2300 nm range and IR VASE was used for MIR spectral region. VASE measurements were performed at different angles of incidence i.e., 50°, 60° and 70° with 10 nm step on BK7 substrates and 65°, 70° and 75° with 10 nm step on silicon substrates. The back side of the samples (BK7) was covered with scotch tape to avoid incoherent backside reflections.

The surface roughness of films was measured by an amplitude-modulated atomic force microscopic instrument (AM-AFM, NT-MDT Ntegra 2, Russia). The semi-contact AFM mode has been utilised for all measurements. AFM scans over 2x2 μm, 5x5 μm, and 10x10 μm areas with 512x512 pixel resolution were performed for films on silicon and Si/SiO₂ substrates. AFM images were then analysed using Gwyddion software, image rows were aligned, and RMS (Root mean square) roughness was used for the characterisation of all (co)-sputtered film samples.

Thicknesses of all samples on BK7 substrates were measured by KLA-Tencor P-7 Stylus Profilometer. At least five measurements were taken at the centre of BK7 with approximately ±1

mm distance from the centre. Final thickness figures were arrived at after taking an average of these five values.

The structure of all the prepared films were studied using micro-Raman spectroscopy. Raman spectra were recorded at room temperature with an excitation wavelength of 785 nm using LabRam HR Evolution coupled with an Olympus X100 microscope. Neutral density filters were used to reduce the laser power focused on the sample and to avoid any laser-induced damage. The temperature dependence of the spectra was corrected, and reduced intensity was determined using the Bose distribution function and Shuker Gammon formula³⁶. All spectra were normalised by the division of its maximum intensity value. The Raman spectra were normalized in order to simplify the qualitative Raman spectrum analysis considering the change of the intensity ratio between bands depending on the deposition parameters (power and pressure) or chemical composition.

To obtain photonic waveguides, the multilayered structure was made of a 2 μm -thick lower confinement layer (SiO_2) and a 500 nm-thick Ge-Bi-Se guiding layer. Ridge waveguides of different widths were then fabricated using a classical i-line photolithographic process (MJB4 Suss Microtech mask aligner) followed by a dry etching procedure at low pressure (Corial 200I) combining reactive ion etching (RIE) and inductively coupled plasma ICP etching by optimizing the conditions etching to obtain vertical sidewalls with a limited roughness.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Elaboration of the co-sputtered films in the $\text{GeSe}_2\text{-Bi}_2\text{Se}_3$ pseudo-binary system

The production of co-sputtered films was designed to explore the pseudo-binary system between the two extremes represented by the targets used, i.e. germanium and bismuth selenides. In Table 1, sample numbers 1 to 7 are depositions with GeSe₂ or Bi₂Se₃ single sources. Calculated deposition rates from these depositions from single sources were used to find the individual cathode power combination (C1/C2) and deposition time during the co-sputtering (samples 8-17), to get the required thicknesses and compositions of the Ge-Bi-Se films ³².

Table 1 summarises the main co-sputtering parameters at a pressure of 0.5 Pa and the chemical composition of fabricated films measured by EDS.

Sample Number	RF Power (W)		Thickness (nm (±5))	Deposition Rate (nm min ⁻¹)	EDS Results (at. % (±1))		
	GeSe ₂ (C1)	Bi ₂ Se ₃ (C2)			Ge	Bi	Se
1	5	---	660	0.62	33	---	67
2	10	---	480	2.29	33	---	67
3	20	---	810	6.5	33	---	67
4	30	---	695	12.6	33	---	67
5	---	5	695	1.78	---	44	56
6	---	10	715	5.71	---	44	56

7	---	20	705	14	---	44	56
8	6	16	750	11.55	2	43	55
9	10	17	760	13.76	4	38	58
10	11	16	815	13.48	5	36	59
10	13	15	740	12.98	8	32	60
11	15	13	770	12.66	10	29	61
12	18	12	775	13.24	14	24	62
13	21	11	790	14.35	17	21	62
14	23	9	785	13.79	21	15	64
15	23	7	800	12.73	23	12	65
16	28	6	750	15.12	26	8	66
17	37	5	750	21.43	29	4	67

Table 1. (Co)-Sputtering deposition parameters at a pressure of 0.5 Pa with chemical composition (± 1 at.%) from EDS measurements.

Figure 1 (a) shows the ternary Ge-Bi-Se diagram with chemical composition data of Ge-Bi-Se co-sputtered films deposited from the mixture of two GeSe_2 and Bi_2Se_3 targets. The amorphous nature of fabricated layers with bismuth content up to 36 at.% was confirmed by XRD analysis.

Figure 1. (a) Ge-Bi-Se ternary diagram showing (co)-sputtered GeSe_2 , Bi_2Se_3 and Ge-Bi-Se thin films' composition (red points – amorphous films, blue points – films containing crystalline phases, grey points – GeSe_2 and Bi_2Se_3 sputtered films). (b) Comparison of studied thin films' compositions in the Ge-Bi-Se system from references ^{15-17, 23, 33-35} (where ^{CS}, ^S and ^{TE} stand for co-sputtered, sputtered, and thermally evaporated films, respectively). Ge-Bi-Se glass-forming region is also indicated from reference ¹⁸.

Figure 1(b) shows the amorphous compositions of the co-sputtered films of the present study and the results from the literature ^{15-17, 23, 33-35}. In the co-sputtering deposition technique, allowing high compositional flexibility with a high cooling rate of thin films, the atomic ratio of the three elements has been largely modified, enabling the establishment of a larger amorphous region with higher bismuth content than what can be offered by the glassy domain.

Figure 2 represents the XRD patterns of GeSe_2 , Bi_2Se_3 and selected Ge-Bi-Se (co)-sputtered films. The absence of any characteristic peaks in the XRD data confirms the amorphous nature of GeSe_2 films and Ge-Bi-Se layers with the concentration of Bi up to 36 at.%. Contrary, the Bi_2Se_3 film diffraction pattern reveals the nanocrystalline nature of the layer. X-ray diffractograms of

the Bi_2Se_3 films, together with the respective PDF data card identified crystalline phases are given in the bottom panel of Figure 2. It can be concluded that the main crystalline phases in (co)-sputtered films are different trigonal bismuth-selenium phases, and possibly partly oxidised bismuth (Bi_4O_7) or selenium (Se).

Figure 2. XRD patterns of single cathode GeSe_2 ($\text{Ge}_{33}\text{Se}_{67}$), Bi_2Se_3 ($\text{Bi}_{44}\text{Se}_{56}$) sputtered and co-sputtered Ge-Bi-Se films ($\text{Ge}_5\text{Bi}_{36}\text{Se}_{59}$ and $\text{Ge}_4\text{Bi}_{38}\text{Se}_{58}$), deposited on BK7 substrates at 0.5 Pa. Vertical lines indicate the crystalline phases from different PDF Cards.

3.2 Structural analysis by micro-Raman scattering spectroscopy

To analyze the impact of bismuth content variation on the structural organization of co-sputtered films of the Ge-Bi-Se system, it is essential to first examine the Raman scattering spectra by identifying the important bands and shoulders in the GeSe_2 and Bi_2Se_3 films deposited from a single target as a function of varying deposition parameters (power and pressures).

Figure 3. (a) Raman spectra of GeSe_2 films deposited at an argon pressure of 0.5 Pa and at different cathode power. (b). Raman spectra of GeSe_2 films deposited at cathode power of 20 W and at different argon pressures.

Figures 3 (a) and (b) show the Raman spectra of GeSe_2 films deposited at different cathode powers (by keeping argon pressure constant at 0.5 Pa) and at two different argon pressures (by keeping cathode power constant at 20 W). Main Raman features include a doublet peaking at around 200 and 216 cm^{-1} accompanied by a band around 175 cm^{-1} and a broad low-intensity peak in the 240-330 cm^{-1} range. GeSe_2 Raman spectrum was deconvoluted with Gaussian functions.

A detailed summary of the interpretation of Raman spectra based on structural units and their characteristic vibrational frequencies are presented in Table 2.

Thin film composition	Main structural units involved	Raman vibrational modes cm⁻¹	References
GeSe₂	GeSe _{4/2} tetrahedra or Se-Se bonds	140	37-38
	GeSe _{4/2} tetrahedra (CS)	200	1, 39-40
	GeSe _{4/2} tetrahedra (ES)	216	1, 37, 41
	Ge-Ge bonds in ETH	175 (~270)	40, 42
	Ge ₂ Se _{6/2} units and [Ge-Ge _m Se _{4-m}] (m = 1,2,3,4) entities		
	Se-Se stretching mode at chains, outriggers or rings	235-245	43-44
	Se-Se bonds vibration	265	44-45
	From dimers and short Se _n chains		
F ₂ asymmetric vibration of GeSe ₄ tetrahedra	280-310	43, 45	

Table 2. Summary of structural units and associated vibrational modes in the Raman spectra of GeSe₂ thin films.

From the Raman spectra analysis, it is evident that power and pressure have distinct influences on the structure of GeSe₂ films. In the case of the power, the intensity between the doublet is not altered, aside from a slight difference in the intensity of the Ge-Ge bond. A statistical fluctuation can produce this difference as the energy of sputtered atoms is enough to slightly decrease this effect. According to EDS analysis, the composition varies no more than 1% around stoichiometric value. In the case of pressure, the doublet peak is more affected. The ratio between CS and ES peaks changes with a decrease in the ES peak and a corresponding reduction in the Ge-Ge bond intensity compared to the CS GeSe₄ band. It can be concluded that the structure is more modified by the pressure. (Figure 3 (b)).

Figure 4. Raman spectrum of Bi₂Se₃ films. (a) Films deposited at lower argon pressures (0.25 Pa and 0.5 Pa) and different RF power from 5 to 20 W. (b) Films deposited at higher (1 Pa and 2.5 Pa) argon pressures in comparison with the film deposited at 0.5 Pa along with films' morphology.

Figure 4 (a) shows the Raman spectra of a single source deposited Bi_2Se_3 film prepared at different cathode powers and argon pressures. Generally, four Raman active modes present in Bi_2Se_3 crystals are Eg_1 , A^1_{1g} , Eg_2 and A^2_{1g} positioned at 50, 72.5, 131.5 and 172.5 cm^{-1} respectively, E or A indicating in-plane or out-of-plane lattice vibrations⁴⁶⁻⁴⁷. In Figure 4, distinct and well-separated Raman modes were observed at 70, 127 and 171 cm^{-1} . The Eg_1 mode at 50 cm^{-1} could not be detected due to instrument limitations. We repeated the deposition at different cathode powers (5, 10, and 20 W) and the characteristic Raman modes were found at the same positions. The presence of a significant contribution to Raman spectra at energy around 100 cm^{-1} in the films can be assigned to the Raman active vibration mode of bismuth oxide⁴⁸⁻⁴⁹. Figure 4 (b) is the Raman spectra of Bi_2Se_3 films deposited at 1 Pa & 2.5 Pa and the films' morphology in comparison with the Bi_2Se_3 film at 0.5 Pa. As can be seen from the morphology, the Bi_2Se_3 films deposited at high pressures are very rough and non-uniform. More detailed structural analysis exploiting XPS or EXAFS is required to get a more detailed view of the structure of Bi_2Se_3 thin films.

Figure 5 (a) & (b). Normalised reduced intensity of Raman spectra of Ge-Bi-Se co-sputtered films in comparison with GeSe_2 and Bi_2Se_3 films deposited on BK7 substrate at 0.5 Pa.

Figure 5 presents the Raman spectra of co-sputtered Ge-Bi-Se films. In GeSe₂-Bi₂Se₃ co-sputtered films, bismuth is incorporated into the GeSe₂ glassy network by replacing more germanium than selenium. It is clear that all peaks in GeSe₂ films were distorted and shifted to the lower energy side on the Bismuth addition. The bismuth atom is larger than selenium or germanium (atomic radius Bi=230 pm, Se=120 pm, Ge=137 pm), it is heavier (Bi=208.98 u, Se=78.96u, Ge=72.64 u), and its electronegativity is the same as that of germanium (Bi=2.02, Se=2.55, Ge=2.01). When we incorporate bismuth into the Ge-Se system, the bonding force will change. Since the Raman vibrational frequency is inversely proportional to the reduced mass of constituent elements participating in bond formation, Raman modes will shift to a lower frequency region^{34,50}. During co-sputtering, the interplay between these atoms may result in the formation of new bonds or the modification of existing bonds which in turn affects the vibrational peaks in Raman spectra.

Both major peaks (200 and 216 cm⁻¹) in GeSe₂ were distorted and shifted to the lower energy side on bismuth addition. For the co-sputtered film with lower bismuth content (Ge₂₉Bi₄Se₆₇), the sharp feature of the 200 cm⁻¹ doublet remains less affected, but the relative intensity of the 216 cm⁻¹ band gets considerably reduced. So, it is possible that some fraction of added bismuth interconnects GeSe_{4/2} tetrahedral units through selenium atoms, where the symmetric vibration of GeSe_{4/2} tetrahedra is less affected⁵⁰. With the addition of Bi, the peak at 176 cm⁻¹ due to the Ge-Ge stretching vibrations of ethane-like (ETH) clusters in GeSe₂ appears to overlap with the A_{2g} vibrational mode of Bi₂Se₃^{34,51}. With the increase in bismuth, all peaks are more left-shifted and for the film containing 12 at. % of Bi, the prominent doublet is completely missing but appears with a further increase in Bi concentration (≥15 at.%). In crystalline co-sputtered films (e.g., Ge₄Bi₃₈Se₅₈, Figure 5 (b)), the only visible peak appears at 165 cm⁻¹ seems the Bi₂Se₃ phase

emerges, resulting in the suppression or bleaching of Ge-Ge structural units and complete overlapping of $\text{GeSe}_{4/2}$ tetrahedral modes with lattice vibration of Bi_2Se_3 crystalline structure. The observation of the crystallization limit as a function of the composition in Raman spectroscopy seems less clear than with the DRX approach probably limited by the size and quantity of the nanoparticles compared to the amorphous phase. The presence of these nanoparticles should be taken into account in particular its impact on the optical losses of Ge-Bi-Se rich in Bi waveguides. In conclusion, we can infer that some fraction of added bismuth and $\text{GeSe}_{4/2}$ tetrahedral units interconnected through Se atoms, and heavy bismuth easily breaks the Se-Se chains or ring clusters, and new Bi-Se bonds were formed. The decrease in the peak intensity and their shifting to the lower energy side are closely related to an increase in bismuth concentration in the co-sputtered films.

Figure 6. AFM images of selected co-sputtered Ge-Bi-Se (a&b), single source deposited GeSe_2 (c) and Bi_2Se_3 (d) films, deposited at 0.5 Pa with average thickness ~ 750 nm, and their root-mean-squared (Sq) roughness values (in nm).

AFM results reveal no apparent substrate-related effects. All films on silicon wafers, as well as on Si/SiO₂, show similar roughness characteristics. So, we can infer that the films' thickness ($\geq 650\text{-}700\text{ nm}$) masked any substrate-related effects on the (co)-sputtered films' surface roughness. Figure 6 (a-d) depicts AFM images of a few selected layers. Root mean square (RMS) surface roughness (S_q) of all co-sputtered films is $\leq 0.8\text{ nm}$ indicating the smoothness of obtained films irrespective of the substrates used. However, for single target depositions, roughness values are larger when repeated the experiment at different powers.

3.3 Optical properties

Optical band gap energy values were estimated from the analysis of transmission spectra of the thin films via Tauc relation (E_g^T)⁵². As depicted in Figure 7, the $(\alpha h\nu)^{1/2}$ vs $h\nu$ plots give a linear fit and confirm the indirect nature of the optical transitions according to Tauc's relation⁵². The intercepts on the energy axis give bandgap energy E_g^T ($E_g^T - E_g$ from Tauc's method) and are indicated in Table 3 together with VASE bandgap energy E_g^{CL} (E_g Cody-Lorentz) results. It was found that E_g^T values decreased from 2.07 to 0.73 eV with an increase in bismuth concentration from 0 to 38%, in agreement with VASE results.

Figure 7. $(\alpha h\nu)^{1/2}$ vs Energy ($h\nu$) plots for (co)-sputtered Ge-Bi-Se films together with optical band gap extrapolation.

The optical bandgap energy E_g^{CL} , refractive index n_0 , and film thickness (in nm) values of (co)-sputtered films were determined using VASE32 software with the ‘Three-layer model’ (substrate + thin film + surface roughness with effective medium approximation consisting of 50 % voids). Cody-Lorentz (CL) oscillator model was used to fit GeSe₂ and GeSe₂-Bi₂Se₃ co-sputtered films, while the parametric semiconductor oscillator model was used to fit Bi₂Se₃ films. Obtained results are summarized in Table 3, which also contains the thicknesses of the films measured by profilometry. It is worth noting that the thicknesses determined by both methods (VASE vs profilometry) are in very good agreement. E_g^T values were estimated by considering the high absorption (absorption coefficient $\alpha > 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) part of the spectra⁵³. Photon energy at $\alpha = 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (E_g^{04}) is also tabulated in Table 3 for the calculation of the non-linear refractive index parameter (n_2) in the subsequent section of this article.

Real Composition (From EDS)	<i>Ellipsometry (VASE)</i>			Thickness <i>Profilometry</i> (nm, ±5)	E_g^T (eV, ±0.02)	E_g^{04} (eV, ±0.02)
	Thickness (nm, ±5)	E_g^{CL} (eV, ±0.02)	n_0 (@ 1.55 μm , ±0.01)			
Ge ₃₃ Se ₆₇	810	2.04	2.41	815	2.07	2.24
Ge ₂₉ Bi ₄ Se ₆₇	750	1.55	2.5	755	1.69	1.92
Ge ₂₆ Bi ₈ Se ₆₆	750	1.41	2.61	745	1.50	1.73

Ge₂₃Bi₁₂Se₆₅	800	1.31	2.76	805	1.36	1.59
Ge₂₁Bi₁₅Se₆₄	785	1.24	2.9	790	1.29	1.49
Ge₁₇Bi₂₁Se₆₂	790	1.16	3.19	795	1.17	1.34
Ge₁₄Bi₂₄Se₆₂	775	1.06	3.33	770	1.10	1.25
Ge₁₀Bi₂₉Se₆₁	770	1.00	3.58	770	1.01	1.15
Ge₈Bi₃₂Se₆₀	740	0.90	3.77	745	0.92	1.05
Ge₅Bi₃₆Se₅₉	815	0.73	4.09	815	0.82	0.95
Ge₄Bi₃₈Se₅₈	760	4.17	755	0.73	0.78
Ge₂Bi₄₃Se₅₅	751	4.59	753	---	---
Bi₄₄Se₅₆	695	---	4.62	690	---	---

Table 3. Summary of films' composition together with VASE determined thickness, bandgap energy deducted using Cody-Lorentz oscillator model (E_g^{CL}), refractive index n_0 , thickness from profilometry measurements and E_g from Tauc plot method (E_g^T)

As depicted in Figure 8, E_g^{CL} and n_0 values of co-sputtered films are greatly influenced by bismuth concentration. From Table 3, it can be inferred that, for the amorphous (co)-sputtered Ge-Bi-Se films, the value of optical bandgap energy E_g (E_g^{CL}) decreases from 2.04 eV (film without Bi) to 0.73 eV (film with 36 at.% Bi) and refractive index n_0 at 1.55 μm increases from 2.41 to 4.09. $\text{Ge}_4\text{Bi}_{38}\text{Se}_{58}$ and $\text{Ge}_2\text{Bi}_{43}\text{Se}_{56}$ films are crystalline, as revealed by XRD and those samples were fitted with the different oscillator models; hence, there are no E_g^{CL} values. Figure 9

shows how the refractive index varies with wavelengths for different films in the VIS/NIR to MIR range.

Figure 8. Variation of refractive index n_0 at 1.55 μm and optical band gap energy (E_g^{CL}) in (co)-sputtered amorphous Ge-Bi-Se films with Bi concentration.

Figure 9. Refractive index dispersion in (co)-sputtered amorphous Ge-Bi-Se films in the VIS/NIR to mid-IR range.

It was found that the optical properties of co-sputtered films could be tuned to a large extent by setting various power combinations C1/C2. Ellipsometric measurements on all films mentioned

in Table 3 were repeated with silicon and Si/SiO₂ substrates. No noticeable change in refractive index or E_g^{CL} values was observed, and it confirmed that substrate has no effect on the optical properties of co-sputtered films.

3.4 Calculation of Non-Linear Optical Parameters

Using semi-empirical Miller's rule ⁵⁴, linear (χ^1) and nonlinear (χ^3) susceptibilities and Kerr coefficient n_2 were calculated for the co-sputtered Ge-Bi-Se films at telecommunication wavelength (1550 nm), with an increase in bismuth content. Miller's relation describes how linear and nonlinear refractive indices are directly related to susceptibility values. A comparison between these predicted n_2 values for Ge-Bi-Se films at 1.55 μm with other Se-based glasses/films from references (T. Cardinal et al. ⁵⁵, Lenz et al. ⁵⁶ Harbold et al. ⁵⁷, Wang et al. ⁵⁴, Nemec et al. ⁵⁸, Olivier et al. ⁴³, Halenkovic et al. ^{27,31}, Dory et al. ³⁸) are illustrated in Figure 10 (a) (n_2 values are either directly taken from references or calculated using the reported n_0 values). The predicted trend is consistent with experimental n_2 values reported by T. Cardinal et al. ⁵⁵ and Harbold et al. ⁵⁷ for AsSSe glasses, Lenz et al. ⁵⁶ for As₂Se₃ glasses, Olivier et al. ⁴³ for GeSbSe glasses, Kuriakose et al. ⁵⁹ and M. Grayson et al. ⁶⁰ for GeSbSe waveguides. Wang et al. ⁵⁴ reported good correspondence between experimental and calculated third-order optical nonlinearities for 51 chalcogenide glasses in the near-infrared region using semi-empirical Miller's rule. Figure 10 (b) showcases these agreements as a plot of n_2 versus n_0 . This list is not exhaustive; several other studies that measured n_2 were excluded either due to a lack of precise linear refractive index values or because their measurements were conducted at wavelengths other than 1.55 μm . Nonlinear refractive index n_2 can also be calculated using Ticha-Tichy formalisms ⁶¹. Ticha and Tichy's model is based on the Wemple-DiDomenico single oscillator model (WD) in combination with the generalised Miller's rule and represents Kerr coefficient values in the limit of $h\nu \rightarrow 0$.

Figure 10 (a). n_2 as a function of n_0 calculated using Miller's equation for Ge-Bi-Se films (this study) compared to other Se-based glasses or films from references at 1.55 μm ; GeSbSe glass^{43, 54, 58}, AsSSe glass^{55, 57}, AS₂Se₃ glass^{54, 56}, GeAsSe glass⁵⁴, GeSbSe films^{27, 38}, GeSbSeTe films^{54, 58}, GaSbSe film³¹, GeSeTe films³⁸. **(b).** Experimental results of n_2 at 1.55 μm for GeSbSe glass^{43, 54}, AsSSe glass^{55, 57}, AS₂Se₃ glass^{54, 56}, GeAsSe glass⁵⁴ and GeSbSe waveguide⁵⁹⁻⁶⁰ demonstrate a close correlation with Miller's theoretical predictions (solid line).

Another model with which the predicted n_2 results can be quantitatively compared is the Sheikh Bahae model⁶², which is based on the Kramers-Kronig transformation and the two-parabolic band model. According to Kramers-Kronig analysis, the value of n_2 , its scaling and dispersion are associated with changes in the nonlinear absorption coefficient through the entire spectrum and vice versa. Different causes like two-photon absorption (2PA), Stark effect and Raman effect could make a considerable variation in n_2 near bandgap and can be theoretically deduced as a function of dispersion function $G_2(h\nu/E_g)$ ⁶² using band gap energy E_g and linear refractive index n_0 .

When we calculated n_2 for the Ge-Bi-Se films using Sheikh Bahae formalism at 1.55 μm , it was observed that n_2 increases up to 8 at.% of Bi (EDS composition Ge₂₆Bi₈Se₆₆) and then decreases gradually with further increase in bismuth content. Table 3 shows that in the EDS composition of

Ge-Bi-Se films, optical bandgap energy decreases while the linear refractive index increases with increasing bismuth at.%. The estimated tendency for n_2 does not align with the n_2 results predicted by Miller's model. Similar trends were reported by Dory et al.³⁸ and Halenkovic et al.⁶³ for some of the GeSbSe, GeSbSeTe films with lower bandgap energies. This variation of n_2 with linear refractive index n_0 at 1.55 μm is illustrated in Figure 11.

Figure 11. n_2 values calculated with Sheik Bahae formalism at 1.55 μm for Ge-Bi-Se films (this study) in comparison with GeSbSe^{27,63} and GeSbSeTe^{27,63} films from literature.

Most of the reported theoretical or experimental studies of n_2 were concentrated on wavelengths below the two-photon absorption edge ($E_g/2$), and observed linearly increasing n_2 values with linear refractive index n_0 . This behaviour of n_2 is also included in Figure 11 for GeSbSe films²⁷. Considering the 2PA condition⁶⁴ i.e. $E_g/2 < h\nu < E_g$, where E_g is the bandgap energy and ν is the optical frequency, our calculations are consistent with the results put forward by Sheik Bahae et al.⁶⁵. Their results indicate that n_2 is negative at wavelengths (energy) well above the 2PA edge ($E_g/2$), and positive at wavelengths below this threshold. In this study, it is confirmed that, at telecommunication wavelength (1.55 μm , $h\nu=0.8$ eV), n_2 increases with the increase in bismuth

concentration up to 8 at % of Bi ($E_g=1.41$ eV) and at 12 % of Bi ($E_g=1.31$ eV) n_2 starts decreasing and becomes negative with any further increase in the bismuth. This highlights, for negative values of n_2 , the limits of the Sheik-Bahae model as a function of the band gap values of the material considered. Thus for films with an atomic percentage of Bi $\geq 8\%$ satisfy the 2PA condition $h\nu > E_g/2$, leading to a decrease in n_2 values.

Due to the lower bandgap energy values of fabricated Ge-Bi-Se layers, the dispersion and magnitude of non-linear refractive indices n_2 at different mid-IR wavelengths (1.55, 2, 2.5, 3, 3.5 and 4 μm) were theoretically analysed. Ge-Bi-Se co-sputtered films studied in this work are amorphous indirect bandgap semiconductors; hence, one can expect a certain extent of uncertainty in the calculations. Figure 12 (a) depicts the dependence n_2 on bismuth concentration at different specified wavelengths calculated using Sheik Bahae's model for all considered amorphous Ge-Bi-Se films.

Figure12. (a) Dependence of calculated non-linear refractive index n_2 on Bi concentration at different wavelengths for amorphous (co)-sputtered Ge-Bi-Se films, derived using Sheik Bahae's equation. (b) Calculated n_2 values for GeSbSeTe films at similar wavelengths illustrating the behaviour of n_2 above and below the 2PA edge ⁶³.

From Figure 12 (a), at higher wavelengths (3, 3.5 and 4 μm), the calculated n_2 values increase with bismuth content. Contrary, in the case of lower wavelengths (1.55 to 2.5 μm), n_2 increases to a certain proportion of bismuth and then decreases and eventually becomes negative. Figure 12 (b) depicts the n_2 values calculated from reference Halenkovic et al. ⁶³ for GeSbSeTe at similar wavelengths. n_2 calculations were done both below and above the 2PA edge, and it clearly demonstrates the dispersive nature of n_2 in lower band gap energy materials. From Figure 12 (a), the n_2 value at 4 μm is lesser than the n_2 value at 3 μm for all film compositions. Considering the lower bandgap energy values of Ge-Bi-Se co-sputtered films at higher bismuth content, it is evident that one can use Ge-Bi-Se co-sputtered films for telecommunication application (1.55 μm , $h\nu = 0.8$ eV) at lower bismuth concentrations (up to 8 or 10 Bi at %). In addition, wavelengths of 3 μm ($h\nu = 0.41$ eV) and beyond can be considered as optimal operating wavelengths for non-linear mid-infrared optical applications at higher atomic percentages of bismuth (> 10%), enabling very high n_2 values to be achieved. At 3 μm , the highest n_2 values obtained are 1.78×10^{-16} m^2/W (Sheik-Bahae model) and 1.20×10^{-16} m^2/W (Miller's rule) for the $\text{Ge}_5\text{Bi}_{36}\text{Se}_{59}$. Similarly, the predicted lowest n_2 values are 8.5×10^{-18} m^2/W (Sheik-Bahae model) and 5×10^{-18} m^2/W (Miller's rule), respectively, for the composition $\text{Ge}_{29}\text{Bi}_4\text{Se}_{67}$. For GeSe_2 ($\text{Ge}_{33}\text{Se}_{67}$) sample, calculated n_2 values are 2.68×10^{-18} m^2/W (Sheik-Bahae model) and 3.47×10^{-18} m^2/W (Miller's rule) respectively at 3 μm .

It is interesting to note that the nonlinear refractive index value increases tenfold when the bismuth content increases from 4 to 36 at. %, where all compositions are amorphous. An increase in n_2 can be due to a number of effects. The introduction of Bi in the glass structural network of GeSe_2 is impacting and modifying the glass network. Bismuth's large atomic radius can result in high polarizability and hyperpolarizability, high linear refractive index, and hence

higher non-linear refractive index. Bi-chalcogen bonds alter the equilibrium between charged defect centres and suppress positively charged structural defects^{20,22}. This significant change in the local structural order, combined with the polarizability of the bismuth, can significantly increase both linear and nonlinear refractive index values. Band gap energy has an inverse influence on linear and non-linear refractive index as per Moss's rule⁶⁶. Thus, the addition of Bi to the GeSe₂ glassy system decreases the bandgap energy and simultaneously increases refractive index values.

The 2PA coefficient (β) value of co-sputtered Ge-Bi-Se films were calculated using the Sheik-Bahae method, which involves the two parabolic band model⁶². Nevertheless, the Heaviside step function in the equation makes β values zero at 3 μm for all compositions except Ge₅Bi₃₆Se₅₉ ($\beta=0.83*10^{-11}$ m/W). Halenkovic et al.²⁷ discussed this behaviour in the case of GeSbSe co-sputtered films at telecommunication wavelength. In amorphous chalcogenides, localised states in the bandgap could serve as in-between resonant levels for cascaded two-step photon absorption. It will result in unusual NLO properties and significant deviations from theoretical predictions. The figure of merit (FOM) is an essential parameter in optical device development, and one should consider the trade-off between high non-linearity and TPA-induced optical losses. For calculating FOM, the β value is chosen as $1*10^{-11}$ m/W for the films under study. Consequently, the variation of FOM with Bi concentration is depicted in Figure 13. In this study, the maximum calculated FOM at 3 μm wavelength is 1.68 for the composition Ge₈Bi₃₂Se₆₀.

Figure 13. Variation of FOM with Bi concentration in amorphous Ge-Bi-Se (co)-sputtered films.

Some studies⁶⁷⁻⁶⁸ pointed out that the optical band gap of amorphous materials is the energy at which absorption reaches 10^4 cm^{-1} . As band gap energy is one of the main decisive parameters in the theoretical prediction of nonlinear optical properties, it is reasonable to analyse the role of E_g in the calculation of n_2 values of Ge-Bi-Se films. Kerr nonlinearities for films were estimated by considering E_g^{04} values using the Sheik Bahae model. Figure 14 shows a comparison between calculated n_2 values using the Sheik Bahae model at different wavelengths using E_g^{CL} or E_g^{04} .

Figure 14. Comparison of nonlinear refractive index n_2 calculated at different Ge-Bi-Se amorphous film compositions using Sheik Bahae model by means of bandgap energy E_g^{CL} or E_g^{04} at 1.55 and 3 μm wavelengths.

The differences in n_2 values are because the photon energy at $\alpha = 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (E_g^{04} , Table 3) is larger than the band gap energy deducted using the Cody-Lorentz oscillator method (E_g^{CL}), and Kerr refractive index has a strong correlation with bandgap and linear refractive index values. Dory et al.⁶⁹ observed a good agreement between n_2 values calculated using the Sheik Bahae method (E_g^{04}) and experimentally measured n_2 values for GeSbSe films. Another model for predicting the dispersion of n_2 for indirect bandgap semiconductors was suggested by Dinu et al.⁷⁰, which predicts maximum nonlinearity n_2 at $0.65 \cdot E_g$, slightly higher than the Sheik-Bahae formula, where it was about $0.53 \cdot E_g$. Defective bonds in amorphous chalcogenide materials can form intermediate states in the band gap and may cause additional nonlinear effects leading to discrepancies between experimental and predicted results⁵⁴.

Since all Ge-Bi-Se films mentioned in this work are amorphous indirect bandgap materials, these NLO calculations from the corresponding linear optical parameters can be considered approximations and require experimental validations to confirm our predictions. To the best of our knowledge, no literature data is available for the experimental determination of non-linear optical properties of Ge-Bi-Se films. Co-sputtered Ge-Bi-Se chalcogenide films with varying compositions and the possibility to tune their properties might have promising applications in photonics due to their rapidly increasing NLO properties and large amorphous regions.

3.5 Ge-Bi-Se Waveguides

The ridge waveguide structures were designed by using commercial software (FIMMWAVE by Photon Design) to obtain the geometrical dimensions, width (w) and height (h), to obtain single mode waveguide at 1550 nm according to the different compositions. The waveguide structure is composed of Ge-Bi-Se films deposited by RF-magnetron sputtering on thermally oxidized silicon. The results are reported in Figure 15. Single-mode guides could be obtained with a thickness of 500 nm and widths ranging from 600 to 800 nm (as shown in Figure 15 (b)) by using a guiding layer based on $\text{Ge}_{28}\text{Bi}_7\text{Se}_{65}$. Otherwise in the case of a guiding layer based on $\text{Ge}_{15}\text{Bi}_{23}\text{Se}_{62}$ characterized by a stronger index contrast, smaller dimensions in the range of 400 to 600 nm (Figure 15 (a)) were acquired.

Figure 15. Evolution of the TE single mode region as a function of width (w) and height (h) of the integrated waveguide of Ge-Bi-Se-on-SiO₂ waveguides from $\text{Ge}_{15}\text{Bi}_{23}\text{Se}_{62}$ (a) and $\text{Ge}_{28}\text{Bi}_7\text{Se}_{65}$ (b). The confinement factor corresponds to the confinement of the propagated light in the guiding layer.

Furthermore, to obtain these integrated ridge waveguides, the etching of the guiding layer based on Ge-Bi-Se films was studied according to the experimental condition to obtain vertical side

with a low roughness. Initially, the Reactive Ion Etching (RIE) and Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP) etching techniques were applied using only CHF_3 gas (5 sccm CHF_3 , 5 mTorr, 75 W ICP, 25 W RF). However, these conditions reveal an important roughness on the side that was strongly tilted, as shown in Figure 16 (a) and (b) regardless of the specific composition of Ge-Bi-Se films. Otherwise, the use of a mixture of CHF_3 and Argon gas (4 sccm CHF_3 , 16 sccm Ar, 5 mTorr, 75 W ICP, 25 W RF) permits to obtain vertical sidewall with a low roughness as illustrated in Figure 16 (c). Figures 16 confirm these observations associated with very low roughness values. As a result, ridge waveguides based on Ge-Bi-Se films could be fabricated by using conventional technological processes, and the injection of light at $1.55 \mu\text{m}$ was achieved in these optical waveguides where optical losses must be optimized. Optimisation of etching parameters for improving overall waveguide performance, better light confinement, and low vertical sidewall roughness to achieve lower propagation losses in Ge-Bi-Se waveguides aimed at nonlinear optical and stimulated Brillouin scattering applications are in progress.

Figure 16. SEM images of Ge-Bi-Se waveguides according to used gas during the etching: etching using CHF_3 gas (5 sccm CHF_3 , 5 mTorr, 75 W ICP, 25 W RF) from $\text{Ge}_{15}\text{Bi}_{23}\text{Se}_{62}$ (a), $\text{Ge}_{28}\text{Bi}_7\text{Se}_{65}$ (b) and etching using CHF_3 and Argon gas (4 sccm CHF_3 , 16 sccm Ar, 5 mTorr, 75 W ICP, 25 W RF) from $\text{Ge}_{28}\text{Bi}_7\text{Se}_{65}$ (c)

4. CONCLUSIONS

Analysis of the prepared Ge-Bi-Se films revealed that the co-sputtering deposition technique noticeably broadens the amorphous region with significantly higher Bismuth atomic percentage (up to at. % Bi = 36%). Repeating optical characterisations and roughness measurements on films deposited on different substrates confirmed that these (co)-sputtered films show no substrate-dependent characteristics. The co-sputtered films exhibit good optical quality as evidenced by their transmission spectra, their characterization by ellipsometry and also confirmed by a surface roughness of the order of ≤ 0.8 nm. With the incorporation of Bi in co-sputtered films, a significant overlap was observed between the prominent Raman peaks of GeSe₂ and Bi₂Se₃ films, accompanied by a redshift in their position. For the film with 12 at. % of Bi (Ge₂₃Bi₁₂Se₆₅), the characteristic Raman doublet of g-GeSe₂ was no longer detectable revealing an alteration of the GeSe₂ network to succeed in incorporating the entities associated with the presence of Bi until reaching a saturation point causing the crystallization of the films towards 36% Bi in the case of co-sputtering fabrication. These thin films were fabricated from two polycrystalline targets of GeSe₂ and Bi₂Se₃ by varying the deposition conditions of the individual targets in the hope of increasing the incorporation of Bi while respecting the amorphization of the thin film. An increase in linear refractive index value n from 2.4 (± 0.01) (Bi at. % = 0) to 4.09 (± 0.01) (Bi at. % = 36) from ellipsometry measurements at telecommunication wavelength indicate the optical properties of Ge-Bi-Se films are greatly inclined to the atomic percentage of bismuth. Theoretical models were used for the in-depth calculation of the non-linear refractive index in the 1.55 to 4 μm wavelength range, and the results were analysed. Among the amorphous co-sputtered films considered in this study, theoretically predicted maximum n_2 values at 3 μm is, $1.78 \times 10^{-16} \text{ m}^2/\text{W}$ from the Sheik-Bahae model and $1.20 \times 10^{-16} \text{ m}^2/\text{W}$ (Miller's rule) (for the film Ge₅Bi₃₆Se₅₉). By means of n_2 and FOM calculations, co-sputtered Ge-Bi-Se films with high bismuth atomic

percentage (>10%) are more suitable for nonlinear optical applications in the MIR wavelength range and this system can effectively be used for telecommunication applications at low bismuth concentrations like the $\text{Ge}_{28}\text{Bi}_7\text{Se}_{65}$ composition. The maximum calculated FOM at 3 μm wavelength is 1.68 for the composition $\text{Ge}_8\text{Bi}_{32}\text{Se}_{60}$. Ge-Bi-Se ridge waveguides were successfully fabricated, and process optimisation is underway to reduce sidewall roughness and propagation losses. It was found that using a mixture of CHF_3 and Argon gas is the most effective method to obtain a vertical sidewall with a low roughness compared to using CHF_3 alone. High third-order nonlinearity, low two-photon absorption, and good light confinement due to the high linear refractive index of amorphous Ge-Bi-Se films/waveguides reported in this study can facilitate the development of next-generation environmentally friendly, arsenic-free photonic integrated circuits operating beyond the telecommunication wavelengths. With these reported insights, Ge-Bi-Se films can be further explored to optimize their LO/NLO behaviour for applications such as optical switching, high-speed optical communication, integrated photonics systems, and acoustic-optical applications.

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